

Reconstructing the Holy Loch Ecosystem: DNA-barcoding and taxonomic assignment protocols used in the Holy Loch Food Web Project (to December 2025).

1. Study Sites and Environmental Measurements

Two sampling locations were established within Holy Loch Nature Reserve on the Cowal Peninsula of Argyll.

Carr Woodland: Flat terrain dominated by *Alnus glutinosa*, *Salix capraea*, and *Betula pubescens* with typical ground flora for damp woodland. This has regenerated on top of an abandoned roads waste landfill site.

Habitat Mosaic: A complex of *Festuca rubra* and *Agrostis stolonifera*-dominated upper saltmarsh, typical saltmarsh pools, a newly-discovered freshwater flush, and a sea-facing shingle ridge vegetated by mixed herbs, Gorse (*Ulex europaeus*) scrub and mature woodland. The area experiences variable freshwater input from rainfall (typically 2500mm per annum) and spring tidal inundations.

2. Invertebrate collection

A Malaise trap was placed at each location monthly at around the same time of each month, during spells of calmer, finer weather, and at least 21 days apart. In March to November, the trap was left out for around 24 hours with 100% ethanol as collection fluid. In December to February, this time was extended to 7 days. Given the strong winds and onshore breezes at the exposed saltmarsh site, the trap was placed on the south-westerly side of a broadleaved woodland in April and May to protect the trap from strong onshore, south-easterly breezes during sunny weather (Grid ref: 55.9941 N, -4.5980; what3words: phantom.overgrown.junction). In June to March, the trap was placed on the seaward side of this woodland to protect from prevailing westerlies funneled down Glen Lean to the river Clyde (55.9945 N, -4.5983; what3words: standard.sunflower.beginning).

3. Molecular pipeline and DNA barcoding

Specimens were processed through the UK BIOSCAN high-throughput pipeline at the Wellcome Sanger Institute as described by Park et al. (2023). Specimens were submerged in a lysis buffer, which allowed seepage of DNA-containing body fluids through the insects' exoskeleton and preserved the structure of the "voucher" specimen for any subsequent taxonomic examination.

The PCR technique was then employed to produce multiple copies of a ca. 658 base pair fragment of the mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) gene present in the DNA lysates (Mullis et al., 1986). The amplified DNA strands were sequenced using the PacBio Sequel II and Revio platforms. Consensus sequences were generated using the mBRAVE bioinformatics pipeline (Ratnasingham, 2019) to isolate high-quality barcodes of around 658 nucleotides, which were then uploaded to the Barcode of Life Data System (BOLD) under project HLNR.

4. Taxonomic assignment and the BIN system

Sequences were analysed using the BOLD identification and classifier tool, operated by the team at the University of Guelph. The identification engine compared sequences against BOLD's reference library of named specimens to provide taxonomic assignments. Sequences were then assigned to Barcode Index Numbers (BINs) using the BOLD Refined Single Linkage (RESL) algorithm (Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2013). This system clusters sequences into statistically distinct operational taxonomic units (OTUs) which serve as high-resolution species proxies, enabling consistent molecular-based taxonomic units even for specimens that lack formal taxonomic identification.

Sequences ending at genus were subsequently investigated by executing manual BLASTn searches against both the Barcode of Life Data System (BOLD) and the GenBank sequence repositories. The rationale for this manual approach is that errors in reference sequence species-level identification within public databases are a frequent cause of ambiguous, genus-only labels.

The criteria for **manual resolution** were:

Taxonomic consistency: The sequence was assigned to a species only if the top ten high-similarity hits in both BOLD and/or GenBank were taxonomically consistent (i.e. belonged to the same species). Where that was not possible, the various possible species were noted.

Sequence Identity: The assigned species had to exhibit a minimum 98% sequence identity to a previously published, high-quality reference sequence.

Publication Record: The accession number of the top hit was reviewed to confirm its association with any published scientific study supporting the species designation.

Sequences that remained taxonomically ambiguous were retained in the dataset and reported as genus-level identifications (e.g., Genus X sp.).

4. Sequence Database

Raw sequences and any taxonomic identifications produced by the BOLD Classifier Engine, (along with some metadata) were downloaded from the Bioscan Report Card website (<https://bioscan.tol.sanger.ac.uk/report-card>).

5. BIN Categorisation at Holy Loch Nature Reserve

To aid future updating of BIN names from either the regular algorithm run at BOLD and new, future barcode generation at Holy Loch Nature Reserve, various factors were taken into consideration in assessing the soundness of BIN naming. These criteria are detailed in Table 1 (Hammatt, 2025; doi:10.5281/zenodo.18094319).

6. Curation

Vouchers will be curated at the Natural History Museum, Cromwell Road, London. Each specimen has unique identifier in the format HLNR_X_YN, where HLNR is the name of the project, X is the number of the 96 well plate, Y is the for plate well row (A to H) and N is the column (1 to 12). Hence HLNR_088_A1 is plate 88, row A and column 1. This code is the unique identifier of the material, and each has its own metadata page on BOLD.

7. References

Hammatt, N. (2025). Confidence criteria used for BIN taxonomic conclusions at Holy Loch Nature Reserve. Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18094319.

Mullis, K., Faloona, F., Scharf, S., Saiki, R., Horn, G., & Erlich, H. (1986) Specific enzymatic amplification of DNA in vitro: the polymerase chain reaction. Cold Spring Harbor Symposia on Quantitative Biology 51, 263-73. doi: 10.1101/sqb.1986.051.01.032.

Park, N., Dawson, E., Thurston, S., Tuameh, A., Mosca M.M., Pereira da Conceicao, L. et al. (2023) High-throughput DNA barcoding library construction and sequencing protocol for BIOSCAN using unpurified non-destructively extracted DNA from arthropods. <https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.8epv5jzxd11b/v1>.

Ratnasingham, S. & Hebert, P.D.N. (2013). A DNA-based registry for all animal species: The Barcode Index Number (BIN) system. *PLoS ONE*, **8**, e66213. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0066213>

Ratnasingham, S. (2019). mBRAVE: The Multiplex Barcode Research And Visualization Environment. Biodiversity Information Science and Standards.